

Final Report

1 General Information

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Title of the project: *Formulation and numerical computation of the low frequency mean flow of fluids*
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2 Summary

Das oszillatorische Verhalten von partiellen Differentialgleichungen, die die Dynamik in der Atmosphäre und den Ozeanen beschreiben, ist eine Herausforderung für das Verständnis der zugrundeliegenden Physik und das Design von effizienten numerischen Verfahren. Die zu betrachtenden Probleme nehmen die folgende Form an

$$\frac{du}{dt} + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \mathcal{L}u + \mathcal{N}(u) = 0. \quad (1)$$

Dabei ist ε ein kleiner Parameter, \mathcal{L} ein schiefhermitischer linearer Operator, der für das oszillatorische Verhalten des Problems verantwortlich ist, und \mathcal{N} ein nicht-linearer Term. Die schnellen Oszillationen haben zwei wichtige Konsequenzen. Erstens, je schneller die Oszillationen sind, umso kleiner ist der benötigte Zeitschritt beim numerischen Verfahren. Zweitens, diese schnellen Oszillationen sind auch verantwortlich für die Bildung des niederfrequenten Grundstroms, die in der Theorie über resonante und fast resonante Wechselwirkungen behandelt wird. Die Thematik des Projekts umfasste den niederfrequenten Grundstrom von Fluiden, der ein zeitlich gemittelter Grundstrom ist und das Verhalten des Fluids auf langsamen Zeitskalen repräsentiert. Für die Untersuchungen wurden die rotierenden Flachwassergleichungen (RSWE) und die Boussinesq Gleichungen verwendet, neben Systemen gewöhnlicher Differentialgleichungen, die als einfachere Prototypbeispiele nützlich waren, und auch die Flachwassergleichungen mit Bathymetrie. Als wichtigste Ergebnisse können angeführt werden:

- 1) Es wurden neue Formulierungen des Grundstroms entwickelt und untersucht. Dabei wurde eine Transformation verwendet, deren Idee mit der *method of cancellation of oscillations* [16] verbunden ist, sowie analytische Mittelungsverfahren.
- 2) Die entwickelten Formulierungen für den Grundstrom wurden verwendet, um neue Zeitintegratoren vom Prediktor-Korrektor-Typ für oszillatorische Differentialgleichungen zu entwickeln. Für die Zeitintegratoren wurde ein Mehrgitter-Ansatz verwendet. Außerdem sind die Zeitintegratoren parallelisierbar und deshalb vielversprechend für Computer mit großer Parallelität.

Eine wichtige Eigenschaft der neuen Formulierungen besteht darin, dass sie sowohl die resonanten als auch die fast resonanten Oszillationen, die durch die Nichtlinearität entstehen, berücksichtigen. Insbesondere kann man bei der neuen Herangehensweise einstellen, welche Moden langsam genug sind, um Teil des Grundstroms zu sein. Dazu wurden Untersuchungen mit den Boussinesq Gleichungen durchgeführt. Die Formulierungen sind für die numerischen Zeitschrittverfahren von Nutzen, insbesondere für einen guten Prediktor-Schritt. Bei der Entwicklung des Zeitschrittverfahrens wurden folgende Punkte abgearbeitet: rekursive Formulierung des Mehrgitterverfahrens, das das Parareale Verfahren [12] mit Mittelungsverfahren und der Transformation kombiniert; die Herleitung einer Fehlerschranke und eines Modells für den Rechenaufwand, das die Parallelität des Verfahrens berücksichtigt; Implementierung von numerischen Beispielen. Dabei wurden ermutigende Untersuchungen hinsichtlich der Effizienz der Mehrgitterverfahren durchgeführt, insbesondere für die rotierenden Flachwassergleichungen.

The oscillatory nature of partial differential equations, which govern the dynamics in the atmo-

sphere and oceans, is a challenge for both understanding the underlying physics and the design of efficient numerical methods. The problems under investigation admit the following form

$$\frac{du}{dt} + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \mathcal{L}u + \mathcal{N}(u) = 0, \quad (2)$$

where ε is a small parameter, \mathcal{L} is a skew-hermitian linear operator, which is responsible for the oscillatory behaviour of the problem, and \mathcal{N} is a non-linear term. The fast oscillations have two important consequences. First, the faster the oscillations, the smaller the time step required in the numerical method. Second, the same fast oscillations are also responsible for forming the low frequency mean flow, which is treated in the theory of resonant and near resonant interactions. The subject matter of the project was the low frequency mean flow of fluids, which is a temporal mean flow and represents the behaviour of the fluid on slow temporal scales. For the investigations the rotating shallow water equations (RSWE) and the Boussinesq equations were studied, besides systems of ordinary differential equations which were used as simpler prototype examples, as well as the shallow water equations with bathymetry. The following main outcomes can be stated:

- 1) New formulations of the mean flow were developed and investigated, using a transformation, related to the *method of cancellation of oscillations* [16], and analytical averaging techniques.
- 2) The novel formulations of the mean flow were used to develop new time integrators of predictor-corrector type for oscillatory differential equations. For the time integrators a multi-grid approach was used. Moreover, the new time stepping methods are parallelisable and therefore promising for computers with large concurrency.

An important feature of the new formulations is that they account for the resonant as well as near resonant frequencies due to the non-linearity. Especially, with the new approach it is possible to adjust which modes are slow enough to be part of the mean flow. For the study of the new formulations, investigations on the Boussinesq equations were carried out. The novel mean flow formulations are beneficial for the numerical time stepping schemes, in particular for a good prediction step. The development of the time stepping methods included the following steps: recursive formulation of a multilevel method, which combines the Parareal method [12], averaging and the transformation; the derivation of an error bound and a model for the computational cost which accounts for the parallelism of the method; implementation of several numerical examples. Encouraging investigations on the efficiency of the multi-level method were carried out, especially for the RSWE.

3 Scientific report on work and results

3.1 Initial questions and objectives

It was a major concern of the project to unite fluid dynamics with numerical analysis and research on numerical algorithms to foster the development of new ideas in the different fields. The focus should be on problems, which admit the form (1), because such problems are relevant for the weather and climate sciences.

Fluid Dynamics

Novel formulations for the mean flow should be investigated and tested on different examples relevant for geophysical fluid simulations. The mean flow should be formulated with the transformation and analytical averaging. The averaging error should be analysed and differences to mean flow formulations obtained with asymptotic analysis should be indicated.

Numerical Analysis

New numerical methods of predictor-corrector type, which can be used to solve problems of form (1), like the RSWE and the swinging spring, should be developed, analysed and tested. These numerical methods should be parallelisable and suitable for high performance computing environments. Consideration should be given to the relation between the time step and the averaging window.

3.2 Scientific findings and results

Problems, which admit form (1), were investigated with respect to suitable numerical time stepping methods and mean flow formulations. Examples of relevance for weather and climate include the RSWE and the Boussinesq equations. Another PDE example studied in the project is shallow water equations with bathymetry. Additionally, several systems of ordinary differential equations (ODE) of the form (1) were investigated. Due to the skew-hermitian linear operator \mathcal{L} , the problem (1) is of oscillatory nature. For the computation of the numerical solutions the following transformation was applied to problem (1)

$$w(t) = \exp\left(\frac{\mathcal{L}}{\epsilon}t\right)u(t). \quad (3)$$

The transformation is related to the *method of cancellation of oscillations*, see [16]. The resulting differential equation is denoted as the *modulation equation* and admits the following form

$$\frac{dw(t)}{dt} = -\exp\left(\frac{\mathcal{L}}{\epsilon}t\right)\mathcal{N}\left(\exp\left(-\frac{\mathcal{L}}{\epsilon}t\right)w(t)\right) = -\tilde{\mathcal{N}}\left(\frac{t}{\epsilon}, w(t)\right). \quad (4)$$

Within the project, the multi-level Parareal method with averaging was developed and examined, see [P1], to solve systems of the form (1). Numerical examples were implemented and made available, see [C2]. The parallelisable time stepping method combines the transformation (3), an analytical averaging technique and the Parareal method, first published in [12]. Problem (1) is reformulated with the transformation (3). Then, the averaging and the Parareal method are used to solve (4). This requires the computation of the exponential of the linear operator \mathcal{L} , which can be done easily if a Fourier discretisation in space is applied. The Parareal method is a parallelisable time stepping method of predictor-corrector type. In a first step, a solution is computed on a coarse grid with a coarse time step. Then a correction is computed in parallel on several fine grids with a smaller time step. The process can be iterated to increase the accuracy of the numerical approximation. For the averaging technique a convolution integral must be evaluated. The averaging is crucial for using big time steps on the coarse grid. Once a solution is computed to problem (4), the result can be transformed back to obtain a solution to problem (1).

Figure 1: Illustration of the multi-level Parareal method with averaging. source: *Multi-level Parareal algorithm with Averaging for Oscillatory Problems*, J. Rosemeier, T. Haut, B. Wingate

The classical Parareal method is a two-level method. The project scientist could build upon a two-level Parareal method with averaging, which was developed earlier, see [9] and [15]. She used a multi-grid approach to generalise the method to multiple levels, see Figure 1. On the different levels the following formulations for the mean flow were used

$$\frac{d\bar{w}_l}{dt} + \frac{1}{\eta_l} \int_{-\eta_l/2}^{\eta_l/2} \rho\left(\frac{s}{\eta_l}\right) \tilde{\mathcal{N}}\left(\frac{s+t}{\varepsilon}, \bar{w}_l(t)\right) ds = 0, \quad (5)$$

for different averaging windows η_l . The function ρ is the kernel function, which is scaled by the averaging window η_l . The index l counts the levels. Only on the finest level, no averaging is applied, i.e. the modulation equation (4) is solved. An error bound was derived for the multi-level method with averaging. The error bound includes the errors made on all levels, whereas earlier error bounds developed for two-level methods included the error of the coarse level only, see [15] or [7]. The error estimated by the error bound is a sum. The terms of the sum represent the errors made on the different levels arising due to time-stepping and averaging. An error contraction can be observed as correction iterations are computed. Moreover, a model for the computational cost, which accounts for the parallelism of the method, was developed for investigations on the efficiency of the new method. Numerical tests were carried out on prototype ODE examples, including the swinging spring, and the RSWE in two parameter regimes, i.e. the incompressible limit and quasigeostrophic limit. Comparison to the earlier developed two-level method showed that the multi-level method can be more efficient.

Problems like the RSWE can have several inherent scales. With the multi-level Parareal method with averaging, a level can be introduced for each scale. Then the averaging window can

Figure 2: Illustration of the diagnostic for the mean flow representation, source: *Mean flow from phase averages in the 2D Boussinesq equations*, B.A. Wingate, J. Rosemeier and T. Haut

be chosen such that the behaviour, which is characteristic for a scale, is resolved on the corresponding level, but the finer behaviour is averaged. Thus, the time step can be chosen such that the features of the scale are resolved but the stiffness from the finer scales does not impose an additional constraint on the time step. The applicability of this approach to models which are more complex than the RSWE including other multi-scale problems can be studied in future work. The results obtained so far were written up in a paper, which is in review and available as a preprint, see [P1].

Moreover, the effect of averaging with different averaging windows η was studied and interpreted in a context related to fluid dynamics. For this, a diagnostic tool was developed, which allows to compare mean flow formulations with different averaging windows to the unaveraged flow, see [P2]. The diagnostic tool was applied to solutions to the Boussinesq equations with different parameters for the buoyancy. First a numerical solution to the Boussinesq equations $u(t)$ was computed. Then, the transformation (3) was applied to the solution $u(t)$ and the solution in the transformed coordinates, denoted as $w(t)$, was obtained. The following formulation for the mean flow in the transformed space was used

$$\bar{w}(t) = \frac{1}{\eta} \int_{-\eta/2}^{\eta/2} \rho\left(\frac{s}{\eta}\right) w(t+s) ds. \quad (6)$$

After evaluating $\bar{w}(t)$, the inverse transformation was applied to get a mean flow for the Boussinesq equations $\bar{u}(t)$, which could then be compared to the unaveraged solution $u(t)$. Figure 2 is an illustration of the diagnostic tool. For the transformation the exponential of the linear operator had to be computed. A Fourier decomposition in space was applied for that.

It was found as a conclusion that the formulations can provide useful representations for the mean flow for different buoyancy parameters. When the averaging technique is applied, an averaging error is introduced. In [P2], it was shown that the averaging error alters the original solution to the Boussinesq equations such that a representation for the mean flow is

Figure 3: averaged time rate of change of the buoyancy in the Boussinesq equations for different averaging windows, source: *Mean flow from phase averages in the 2D Boussinesq equations*, B.A. Wingate, J. Rosemeier and T. Haut

obtained. That means that the averaging error corresponds to the deviation from the mean flow. As formulations with averaging are used, steep gradients are damped, see Figure 3. Such formulations can be beneficial when big time steps shall be used for numerical time stepping methods. The methodology and results were written up in a paper for the case of the decaying Boussinesq equations, see [P2]. Additionally, a paper, in which forcing terms are coupled to the Boussinesq equations, is currently in preparation. (First results indicate that it might be convenient to recompute the interaction coefficients for the problem with forcing, see [13] for interaction coefficients.)

A difference to an earlier approach is that the formulation (6) accounts for slow frequencies with nonzero wave numbers k , too. In this context, slow frequencies are frequencies whose period is bigger than the length of the averaging window η . The fast frequencies, that is the frequencies whose period is smaller than the averaging window, are strongly damped. Thus, with the averaging window it is possible to adjust which frequencies contribute to the particular mean flow formulation.

Results about several examples relevant for the study of fluid flows, including the shallow water equations, show that the leading order asymptotic solution of the fluid equations is determined by a function $\tilde{u}(t)$, for which an integral with an infinite averaging window $\eta \rightarrow \infty$ must be evaluated, see [6, 20] or [10]. Furthermore, it was found, using the Riemann-Lebesgue lemma, that with this approach the slow modes with wave numbers $k \neq 0$ are cancelled, too. Only the mode with zero wave number remains in the solution. However, there exist studies which suggest that other slow frequencies, i.e. near-resonant frequencies, can have an important impact too, see [17, 18]. The results in [P2] indicate that the formulations with finite averaging window show a less complex behaviour than the original solutions but retain more features than solutions,

obtained with an infinite averaging window.

Within the project a coarse propagator with averaging to solve the shallow water equations with bathymetry, also denoted as bottom topography, was implemented. The solutions to the shallow water equations with bathymetry shall be used to solve an optimisation problem, see [2]. The aim of the optimisation problem is to reconstruct the bathymetry. The shallow water equations with bathymetry without smoothing terms are known to develop shocks, which is inconvenient for the optimisation algorithm. Therefore, tests with coupled second and fourth order diffusion terms were made. The results were collected in a jupyter notebook.

The role of the transformation (3) and the kernel function ρ was discussed in the course of the project. The author of [19] proposes a modified transformation and shows that the new transformation can lead to a better approximation of the mean behaviour. The work on new transformations is a direction worth pursuing in future studies. Another possibility to reduce the error is to construct a kernel function ρ such that the stiffness regulator function, see [14], is minimised. To find an improved kernel function ρ , one can try to expand the kernel function in terms of basis functions p_n of a suitable vector space and formulate a minimisation problem for the coefficients of p_n . This leads to a linear minimisation problem. Moreover, versions of the method of spectral deferred corrections (SDC), see [5], were implemented and made available, see [C1]. This time stepping method is of predictor corrector type and there exist parallelisable versions too, see [4].

3.3 Deviations from the initial concept

In the original proposal it was not explicitly stated to develop ideas for numerical time steppers which employ a multi-level approach, though new numerical time stepping methods should be developed. It was proposed to investigate the relation between the time step and averaging window. Interpreting the averaged equations in the context of multi-scale problems led to the idea that the problem formulation with the averaging represents the behaviour of the problem on a certain scale and the time step must be chosen such that it resolves the dynamics on that scale. The choice of the averaging window is crucial for selecting a scale. This paved the way to proposing a parallelisable time stepping method for complex multi-scale problems and was a fortunate development in the project. The project scientist used this opportunity and formulated the ideas in [P1]. In the future, the ideas may be applied to other multi-scale problems to explore the full potential of the new time stepping method, see [11] for scale-dependent models in meteorology that might be solved on different levels.

For the simulations in the second paper, Dedalus, see [3], was used instead of Firedrake/Gusto, see [8, 1]. Dedalus is a framework for solving PDEs spectrally. A delay in using Firedrake/Gusto was caused because of installation issues with the type of computers used by the project scientist. However, the multi-level Parareal method with averaging shall be available in the framework. Dr. Shipton is interested in the multi-level Parareal method with averaging and discussed with the fellowship holder how it can be implemented in Firedrake/Gusto. An implementation in the framework would be beneficial, as REXI, a method to compute exponentials of linear operators, is implemented in Firedrake/Gusto. Also the project scientist and her co-authors decided to

work with the 2d Boussinesq equations in the second paper instead of the rotating shallow water equations to study the effects of the averaging on a problem with buoyancy. The solution of a problem with bathymetry was not explicitly stated in the proposal.

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4 Published project results

4.1 Peer-reviewed work

- [P1] Juliane Rosemeier, Terry Haut, and Beth Wingate. Parareal algorithm with averaging for oscillatory problems. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, (in review), 2023. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2211.17239.pdf>.
- [P2] Beth A. Wingate, Juliane Rosemeier, and Terry Haut. Mean flow from phase averages in the 2d boussinesq equations. *Atmosphere*, 14(10), 2023.

4.2 Other publications (published code)

- [C1] https://github.com/jshipton/intro_to_PinT_algorithms, notebooks used for the workshop *Exascale Computing Challenges: Parallel-in-Time Algorithms* funded by the *ExCALIBUR* programme.
- [C2] Juliane Rosemeier, 2022. Juliane-Rosemeier/Multi-level-Parareal-Examples: ODE examples solved with the Multi-level Parareal method. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7382198>.